

TABLE 1—¹H NMR SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 4-9 (Diastereomers) AND 10-12 (Monomers)*

Comp. no.	C ₂ , ₅ -HAA' C ₃ , ₆ -HBB' C ₃ , ₆ -HXX'		Aromatic		Piperidine		OMe	
	C ₂ , ₅ '-H C ₆ , ₁₃ '-H C ₂ , ₁₁ '-H C ₆ , ₁₃ '-H	C ₃ , ₆ '-H C ₄ , ₁₁ '-H C ₃ , ₆ '-H C ₄ , ₁₁ '-H	C ₂ , ₅ '-H C ₆ , ₁₃ '-H	C ₃ , ₆ '-H C ₄ , ₁₁ '-H	C ₂ , ₅ '-H C ₆ , ₁₃ '-H	C ₃ , ₆ '-H C ₄ , ₁₁ '-H		C ₂ , ₅ '-H C ₆ , ₁₃ '-H
4	2.15	2.50	3.49	←	1.20-1.32 (4H, m)	1.37-1.48 (4H, m)	3.11-3.42 (4H, m)	3.00-3.08 (4H, m)
	J _{AB} 15.0, J _{AX} 3.2, J _{BX} 10.3, J _{XX'} 11.4							
7	2.63	2.68	3.58	←	1.34-1.34 (4H, m)	1.38-1.46 (4H, m)	3.28-3.47 (4H, m)	3.19-3.12 (4H, m)
	(J _{AB} 14.6, J _{AX} 7.9, J _{BX} 6.1, J _{XX'} 7.5)							
5	2.16	2.42	3.37	←	1.19-1.36 (4H, m)	1.34-1.40 (4H, m)	3.13-3.33 (4H, m)	2.97-3.0 (6H, s)
	(J _{AB} 14.4, J _{AX} 2.5, J _{XX'} 9.7, J _{BX} 10.1)							
8	2.59	2.66	3.52	←	1.34-1.42 (4H, m)	1.51-1.53 (4H, m)	3.40-3.45 (4H, m)	3.17-3.24 (6H, s)
	(J _{AB} 14.9, J _{AX} 7.3, J _{BX} 5.9, J _{XX'} 6.0)							
6	2.30	2.43	3.42	←	1.33-1.36 (4H, m)	1.43-1.47 (4H, m)	3.21-3.45 (4H, m)	3.05-3.07 (4H, m)
	(J _{AB} 14.5, J _{AX} 9.2, J _{BX} 10.0, J _{XX'} 11.0)							
9	2.69	2.69	3.53	←	1.38-1.42 (4H, m)	1.49-1.54 (4H, m)	3.38-3.49 (4H, m)	3.17-3.26 (4H, m)
	(J _{AB} 15.1, J _{AX} 7.5, J _{BX} 6.0, J _{XX'} 7.0)							
10	2.51-2.69 (2H, m)	2.87-3.05 (2H, m)		←	1.54 (6H, br, s)		3.53 (2H, m)	3.92 (2H, m)
11	2.56 (2H, A ₂ B ₂ system)	2.88 (2H, A ₂ B ₂ system)		←	1.24-1.60 (6H, m)		3.53 (2H, t, 5.4)	3.75 (2H, s)
12	2.59 (2H, A ₂ B ₂ system)	2.85 (2H, A ₂ B ₂ system)		←	1.45-1.67 (6H, m)		3.5 (2H, t, 5.2)	3.79 (2H, t, 5.9)

*For compounds 10-12 carbon nos. 4, 5, 7', 8', 9', 10', 11', 12', 1", 8", 9", 10", 11" and 12" are absent.

Chemical shifts (δ) and coupling constants (J in Hz) were calculated for C₂,₅-HAA', C₃,₆-HBB', C₃,₆-HXX' by PANTIC program with an accuracy of ±0.2 Hz.

TABLE 2—¹³C NMR SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 4-9 (DIMER) AND 10-12 (MONOMER)

Compd. no.	Aromatic						Piperidine							
	C-1,4	C-2,6	C-3,5	C-1,7'	C-2,8'	C-3,9'	C-4,10'	C-5,11'	C-6,12'	C-3,9''	C-4,10''	C-5,11''	C-6,12''	OMe
4	169.70	37.92	47.80	142.80	128.44	128.30	128.30	128.44	128.44	46.50	25.80	24.26	24.40	26.00
7	169.90	37.41	46.80	142.98	128.59	128.72	128.72	128.59	128.59	46.62	25.98	24.38	24.66	26.12
5	169.86	37.98	47.12	134.92	129.13	113.76	113.76	129.13	129.13	46.48	25.27	24.35	42.38	26.02
8	170.12	37.63	46.77	134.32	129.89	113.12	113.12	129.89	129.89	45.69	25.94	24.49	42.76	26.32
6	170.11	38.33	47.57	135.88	111.67	149.10	112.00	120.57	120.57	46.71	25.50	24.43	42.66	26.26
9	169.69	37.93	46.44	134.56	110.88	147.86	112.24	120.32	120.32	45.81	25.19	24.10	42.40	25.97
10	169.70	34.40	31.00	140.80	125.40	127.80	125.40	125.40	125.40	46.00	24.90	23.90	42.00	25.70
11	170.41	35.20	30.62	138.45	129.20	113.83	113.83	129.20	129.20	46.92	25.43	24.51	42.59	26.39
12	170.41	35.20	31.18	134.25	111.67	149.05	112.20	120.33	120.33	45.66	25.48	24.45	42.65	26.35

TABLE 3—¹H NMR SPECTRAL DATA* OF COMPOUNDS 17, 1, AND 25

Compd. no.	Aromatic			Piperidine		
	C _{5,9} '-H	C _{6,12} '-H	C _{3,10} '-H	C _{2,11} '-H	C _{4,10} '-H	C _{6,12} '-H
17a (meso)	← 3.01 (XX') (2H, m)	2.74 (AA') (4H, m)	2.84 (BB') (4H, m)	← 3.77 (OMe) (6H, s)	← 8.69 (C _{1,4} -OMe) (6H, s)	C _{6,12} '-H (2H, t, 6.5), 2.06-2.09 (3H, m)
17b (di)	← 3.00 (XX') (2H, m)	2.94 (AA', BB') (4H, m)	← 6.79 (4H, d, 8.7)	← 3.78 (OMe) (6H, s)	← 1.12-1.27 (4H, m)	1.12-1.27 (4H, m) 1.79-1.88 (4H, m)
18	← 6.97 (4H, d, 8.6)	← 6.74 (4H, d, 8.6)	← 6.97 (4H, d, 8.6)	← 3.73 (OMe) (6H, s)	← 1.67-1.76 (4H, br m)	1.67-1.76 (4H, br m) 1.44-1.51 (4H, m)
25	← 6.77-6.80 (4H, m)	← 6.97-7.19 (6H, m)	← 6.97-7.19 (6H, m)	← 3.73 (OMe) (6H, s)	← 1.12-1.27 (4H, m)	1.12-1.27 (4H, m) 1.79-1.88 (4H, m)

* δ ppm; J in Hz.

TABLE 4—¹³C NMR SPECTRAL DATA (δ) OF COMPOUNDS 17, 18 AND 25

Compd. no.	Aromatic			Piperidine		
	C _{1,7} '	C _{3,9} '	C _{5,11} '	C _{2,11} '	C _{4,10} '	C _{6,12} '
17a (meso)	180.27	129.75	113.77	158.21	113.77	129.75
17b (di)	180.78	129.87	113.77	158.21	113.77	129.87
18	135.75	129.04	113.61	157.85	113.61	129.04
25	70.60	30.21	50.33	142.58	137.52	137.52

exhibited uv absorption characteristics (λ_{\max} (EtOH) 268, 265, 259, 253, 248 and 217 nm) similar to those of toluene. Its ir spectrum (thin film) showed maxima for an amide at 1625 cm^{-1} and mono-substituted benzene at 775 and 730 cm^{-1} , but lacked the band for an *E*-olefin at 1645 cm^{-1} , which was present in **1**. Its ^1H nmr spectrum (80 MHz) indicated the presence of a CH_2CH_2 side chain (4-proton A_2B_2 system centered at δ 2.60 and 2.98). These data indicated that **10** was the dihydro-derivative of **1**.

Compounds **4** and **7**, $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$, showed uv absorptions (**4**, λ_{\max} (EtOH) 265, 259, 253, 216 nm; $\log \epsilon$ 2.58, 2.68, 2.64, 3.78; **7**, λ_{\max} (EtOH) 265, 259, 253, 221 nm; $\log \epsilon$ 2.58, 2.68, 2.64, 3.78) similar to those of **10**. Their ir spectra showed bands for an amide carbonyl (1650 and 1642 cm^{-1} respectively) and mono-substituted-phenyl (775 , 730 and 775 and 720 cm^{-1} respectively), but lacked bands for olefinic unsaturation. These spectroscopical observations, taken along with their molecular formulae suggested that **4** and **7** were reductive dimers derived from **1**. The mass spectra (75 eV) of these dimers showed the molecular ion peaks at m/z 432. The ^{13}C nmr spectra (75.5 MHz) of **4** and **7** showed the presence of only twelve signals, which indicated the symmetrical nature of these dimers. This was corroborated by the ^1H nmr spectra (300 MHz) which had signals corresponding to half the proton number.

A comparison of the nmr spectra of the six reductive dimers (**4**–**9**), showed close identity in ^1H (Table 1) and ^{13}C nmr (Table 2) characteristics of the non-aromatic portions between **4**, **5** and **6** on one band and **7**, **8** and **9** on the other. Thus compounds **4**–**6** possessed similar structures and relative configurations, the only difference being in the aryl groups. Similarly, compounds **7**, **8** and **9** formed another related series, which was diastereoisomeric with the former.

Thus these dimers could have either the symmetrical α,α' (**13**) or β,β' (**4**–**9**) structures, but the unsymmetrical α,β' -structures (**14**) were definitely excluded. Detailed nmr studies were undertaken to confirm the structure and stereochemistry of these compounds which included recording of ^1H nmr (300 MHz) and ^{13}C nmr (75.5 MHz) spectra, and the COSY-45° , ^1H – ^{13}C -heteronuclear shift correlation by the XHCORR sequence¹⁴. The ^1H nmr spectrum (300 MHz) of **4** showed the presence of an $\text{ABXX}'\text{B}'\text{A}'$ system, the AB and $\text{A}'\text{B}'$ parts appearing at δ 2.19 (A, A') and 2.53 (B, B'), while the X, X' protons resonated at δ 3.54. Decoupling and COSY-45° experiment (Fig. 1) confirmed the coupling behaviour of these protons. The XHCORR spectrum showed that the $\text{A}(\text{A}')$, $\text{B}(\text{B}')$ protons appearing at δ 2.19 and 2.53 were attached to the methylene carbon at δ 38.02, while the $\text{X}(\text{X}')$ proton at δ 3.54 was attached to the methine carbon at δ 47.66.

Compound **7** had broadly similar ^1H and ^{13}C nmr characteristics. It was distinguished from **4**

Fig. 1. COSY-45° 2D-spectrum of **4**—aliphatic portion only.

by the difference in coupling patterns of the $\text{ABXX}'\text{B}'\text{A}'$ system, while the chemical shifts of these protons were changed only slightly. This seemed to indicate that **4** and **7** bore a diastereoisomeric relationship to each other. It therefore seemed to settle the position of linkage in these compounds as well as their relative configurations.

The ^1H chemical shifts of $\text{A}, \text{A}', \text{B}, \text{B}'$ and X, X' of **4** and **7** were similar to those of the benzylic protons and α -protons of **10** respectively which seemed initially to suggest the α,α' -linkage. A consideration of the chemical shifts of the side-chain carbons using additivity parameters was unable to distinguish between the α,α' - and β,β' -possibilities.

A literature search revealed that a paper existed which reported the preparation of a *meso*-diaryl-succinic acid and its dimethyl ester by using the Stobbe condensation route shown in Scheme 1¹⁵. This author contended that the thermodynamically more stable *meso*-isomer was obtained exclusively by hydrogenating the double bonds in **15** by Raney nickel under strongly alkaline equilibrating conditions. Neelima and Bhaduri also reported a similar synthesis of **16** without, however, commenting on the stereochemistry of the products(s)¹⁶. We followed the reported procedure^{15,16} to obtain dicarboxylic acid (**16**) as an amorphous solid. Attempts to convert this acid to the corresponding piperidide met with failure, though several alternative methodologies were tried. An alternative approach to convert the diunsaturated acid (**15**) to the piperidide before hydrogenation also failed.

Hence the acid (16) was converted to the dimethyl ester with diazomethane (this was a diastereoisomeric mixture rather than the pure *meso*-compound, see later for confirmation of this). The ^1H and ^{13}C nmr spectra of this dimethyl ester product was distinctly different from those of 4 or 7 in the following respects: (i) the methylene carbon signals of 4 and 7 were shifted approximately 2–3 ppm upfield, (ii) the methine carbon signals of 4 and 7 appearing at δ 47.80 and 46.80 were shifted approximately 2–3 ppm downfield, and (iii) the methine protons in 4 and 7 appeared 1 ppm or more downfield than the methylene protons, while in the ester 17 they appeared in approximately the same region (δ 2.70–3.03). The replacement of a methyl ester group for a piperidine would not be expected to change the chemical shifts of the side-chain signals to such a great extent. Hence the diastereoisomeric α,α' -structures for the dimers 4 and 7 were ruled out; these therefore had the diastereoisomeric β,β' -structures.

The β,β' -structures for these compounds were confirmed by reduction experiments of 5 and 7. Diborane reductions of these compounds caused conversion of the N–CO group to N–CH₂ group and yielded 18, C₃₀H₄₄N₂O₂, and 25, C₂₈H₄₀N₂ respectively. For compound 25, the methine protons appeared at δ 3.34, more or less the same value as 7, while the α,α' -methylenes shifted upfield. This agreed with the β,β' -linked structure; α,α' -linking would have led to an upfield shift of the methine protons while the positions of the methylene protons would have remained largely unaffected. The coupling pattern of the protons was confirmed by decoupling experiments and by recording the two-dimensional $\text{cosy-}45^\circ$ spectrum (Fig. 2).

It remained to determine the relative configurations (*meso*- or *dl*-) of the two series. This has been achieved by comparing the actual spectra with simulated spectra and arguments based on conformational analysis. The side-chain protons exhibit a ABXX'B'A' pattern, which is distinctly

Fig. 2. $\text{cosy-}45^\circ$ 2D-spectrum of 25 – aliphatic portion only.

different from a simple ABX pattern. The chemical shift and coupling constant parameters could be estimated by using the Bruker software PANIC (Parameter Adjustment in Nmr by Iterative Calculations), which involves spectra simulation on the basis of a set of parameters and comparison with the experimental spectra. The best-fit between experimental and simulated spectra regarding line-intensities and position of peaks, was obtained for the set of parameters given in Table 1 for 4 and 7. These show a J_{xx} , 11.4 Hz for 4 and a J_{xx} , 7.5 Hz for 7.

For the *meso*-isomers, the preferred conformer would be (A), where the $H_x-C-C-H_x$ dihedral angle would be 180° , and hence the coupling constant would be expected to be about 9–12 Hz. Hence the series 4–6 can be assigned the *meso*-configuration with a fair amount of confidence.

For the *dl*-isomers, the three relevant conformations are B–D. Of these D can be ruled out on account of severe steric interactions. In conformation B, though the interaction between the two largest groups are avoided, new $ArCH_2CO$ -piperidinyl interactions are present. Hence it is reasonable to conclude that both conformations B and C would be present for the *dl*-isomers. This would mean that the coupling constant J_{xx} would be somewhat lower than for the *meso*-isomer. This is in agreement with the value observed for the series 7–9.

Thus the structure and stereochemistry of the reductive dimers are as shown by structural formulae 4, 5, 6 for *meso*-series and 7, 8, 9 for the *dl*-series. Compounds 10–12 were the dihydro derivatives obtained by reduction of the three

Fig. 8. XHCORR of 7.

cinnamic acid piperidides. The complete 1H and ^{13}C nmr assignments are given in Tables 1 and 2 respectively. These assignments are supported by $cosy-45^\circ$ and heteronuclear-shift correlation (XHCORR) 2D-NMR experiments. A representative $cosy-45^\circ$ spectrum of 4 and a representative XHCORR spectrum of 7 are shown in Figs. 1 and 3 respectively. The mass spectral fragmentation patterns of the compounds 4–9 have been investigated; that for a typical example, viz. 4, is shown in Scheme 2.

Scheme 2

Reaction mechanism: The mechanism involves the transfer of an electron to the conjugated amide from sodium naphthalenide to give the radical anion 19. The genesis of the products is outlined in Scheme 3. Acceptance of a second electron from sodium naphthalenide gives the dianion (20), which is stabilised by delocalisation of both the negative charges over the carbonyl group and the aryl ring. Protonation during work-up furnishes the dihydro products (10–12). Delocalisation of the negative charge would be less effective in the presence of electron-donating groups like methoxyl on the aryl ring—this led to the observed lowering of relative yields of the dihydro product. Protonation of the radical anion, followed by an electron-transfer in the reaction medium can only be a minor pathway, since the reaction was carried out in an ether solvent of low proton-donating capability.

The radical anion (19) can dimerise to give the dianion (22), which after work-up would lead to the products (4–9). Alternatively, 19 can react with a neutral molecule to give the radical-anion (21), which then accepts an electron from sodium naphthalenide to give 22. The predominant interaction would in either case be between the LUMOs of the reacting species. The geometry of approach of the two reactive species can thus be visualised to

Scheme 3

be either 23 or 24, where favourable secondary interactions would occur at C-2, C-2'. Approach 24 would be favoured on the grounds of lower non-bonded steric interactions and lesser dipole-dipole interactions between the carbonyl group. Thus the product of kinetic control would be the *dl*-isomers (7-9). This is in accordance with the observed product ratios. The reductive dimerisation is a kinetically-controlled process as there is little scope of equilibration during the reaction. The β, β' -coupling is favoured over the α, α' -coupling, as the negative charge in the transition state is better delocalised by the carbonyl group than by the aryl moiety.

Stereochemistry of the ester (17): It was of interest to us to subject the ester (17) to detailed nmr analysis. Both the ¹H (300 MHz) and ¹³C (75.5 MHz) nmr spectroscopy revealed it to be a mixture of diastereoisomers. Detailed analysis of the ¹H nmr spectrum by the PANIC-programme and the study of its COSY-45° and XHCORR (1-bond) 2D-

nmr spectra led to the complete signal assignments (Table 3). Integration of the corresponding ¹H- and ¹³C-signals of the two diastereoisomers revealed that the product ester was a mixture of the *meso* (17a) and *dl* (17b) isomers in the ratio 62:38. Thus the contention of Schrecker that the *meso*-isomer is the sole product is wrong. The *meso*-isomer of course is the predominant isomer by virtue of its greater thermodynamic stability. Our attempts to separate the *meso*- and *dl*-forms of 17 by column chromatography and PTLC proved unsuccessful. It seems probable that all the similar compounds reported by Neelima and Bhaduri are diastereoisomeric mixtures, as were obtained by us.

Experimental

Melting points were recorded on an electrically heated Kofler Block apparatus and are uncorrected. The uv spectra (95% aldehyde-free ethanol) were measured on a Varian 634 S spectrophotometer and

the ir spectra on a Perkin-Elmer 782 spectrophotometer. The ^1H nmr (300 MHz) and ^{13}C nmr (75.5 MHz) spectra as well as 2D-nmr (HOMCOR-COSY and heteronuclear shift correlations by the XHCORR sequence) were recorded with a Bruker AM-300L superconducting magnet nmr spectrometer using a 5 mm ^1H - ^{13}C dual probe and operating with a Bruker DISR 861 software. The ^1H nmr (80 MHz) and ^{13}C nmr (20 MHz) spectra were recorded with a Varian CFT-20 spectrometer in CDCl_3 using TMS as internal standard.

Neutral alumina and silica gel were used for column chromatography, and silica gel G and alumina G for tlc. Organic extracts were dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 . Analytical samples were routinely dried over P_2O_5 under reduced pressure at room temperature.

The starting materials, viz. 1-cinnamoylpiperidine¹¹ and 1-(4'-methoxycinnamoyl)piperidine¹² were prepared by standard methods from the corresponding acids. Their identities were confirmed from their m.p.s., elemental analyses and ir and ^1H nmr spectral data.

1-(3',4'-Dimethoxycinnamoyl)piperidine: A mixture of 3,4-dimethoxy cinnamic acid (10.4 g, 0.05 mol) and thionyl chloride (4.3 ml, 0.06 mol) was refluxed gently for 2 h. Excess thionyl chloride was removed under reduced pressure. The resulting solid acid chloride was dissolved in dry benzene (9 ml) and cooled to 0° , and piperidine (9.9 ml, 0.1 mol) was then added to it dropwise over a period of 2 h with continuous stirring. The reaction mixture was left overnight, diluted with ether and then washed with water. The solvent was evaporated and the amide (3) was crystallised from ether as colourless crystals (9.2 g, 67%), m.p. 74° (Found: C, 69.5; H, 7.5; N 4.9. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{21}\text{NO}_3$ calcd. for: C, 69.8; H, 7.7; N 5.1%); λ_{max} (EtOH) 320, 292, 236, 220 and 209 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.19, 4.16, 4.08, 4.07 and 4.04); ν_{max} (KBr) 1 635 (amide C=O), 850, 800 and 760 cm^{-1} (Ar).

General method for preparation of sodium naphthalenide¹⁰: A slight excess of sodium (~ 1.2 molar proportion) was added to a solution of naphthalene in anhydrous 1,2-dimethoxyethane under dry nitrogen at $5-10^\circ$. The reaction mixture was then stirred for 2 h at that temperature. The resulting solution of the reagent was dark green in colour (the reagent kept for about a day under nitrogen but deteriorated thereafter).

Reaction with 1-(cinnamoyl)piperidine (1): 1-(Cinnamoyl)piperidine (2.5 g, 0.01 mol) in anhydrous 1,2-dimethoxyethane was added at room temperature to a solution of sodium naphthalenide (from 2.04 g, 0.016 mol of naphthalene) in anhydrous 1,2-dimethoxyethane under dry nitrogen. The reaction mixture was stirred for 2 h at room temperature, and then poured into an aqueous buffer solution of citric acid and sodium citrate (pH ~ 4.5). The resulting mixture was extracted with CHCl_3 (3×50 ml). The CHCl_3 extract was washed

successively with aqueous NaHCO_3 and water, dried (anhydrous Na_2SO_4) and concentrated. The concentrated CHCl_3 extract on column chromatography over silica gel furnished **10** (0.64 g, 29.5%) from the benzene-EtOAc (9:1) eluates, **4** (30 mg, 1.4%) from the benzene-EtOAc (4:1) eluates, and **7** (1.3 g, 60.2%) from the benzene-EtOAc (1:1) eluates; **10**, b.p. $143-50^\circ/14\text{ mm}$ (Found: C, 77.1; H, 8.6; N, 6.2. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{19}\text{NO}$ calcd. for: C, 77.4; H, 8.8; N, 6.5%); R_f 0.45 (silica gel G, 4:1 benzene-EtOAc); **4**, m.p. $220-24^\circ$ (Found: C, 77.3; H, 8.1; N, 6.2. $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{36}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$ calcd. for: C, 77.7; H, 8.4; N, 6.5%); R_f 0.29 (silica-gel; 1:1, benzene-EtOAc); m/z (relative abundance %) (M^+ , 432), 307 (10.2), 306 (53.1), 216 (28.6), 112 (base peak), 104 (14.3) and 84 (28.6); **7**, m.p. 108° (Found: C, 77.42; H, 8.11; N, 6.15. $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{36}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$ calcd. for: C, 77.7; H, 8.4; N, 6.5%); R_f 0.28 (silica-gel; 5% MeOH-EtOAc); m/z (relative abundance %) (M^+ , 432), 348 (18), 320 (8), 307 (10), 306 (48), 216 (48), 112 (base peak), 104 (12) and 84 (46).

Reaction with 1-(4'-methoxycinnamoyl)piperidine (2): 1-(4'-Methoxycinnamoyl)piperidine (2.45 g, 0.01 mol) in anhydrous 1,2-dimethoxyethane was added at room temperature to a solution of sodium naphthalenide (from 2.04 g, 0.016 mol of naphthalene) in 1,2-dimethoxyethane under dry nitrogen. The reaction was complete in 3 h. It was worked up in the usual manner and subjected to column chromatography over neutral alumina. Chromatography separated the three products: **11** (0.20 g, 8%) from petrol-benzene (1:1) eluates, and **5** (0.30 g, 12.2%) and **8** (0.80 g, 32.5%) from benzene-ethyl acetate (1:1) eluates. The latter two products (**5** and **8**) were separated from benzene-ethyl acetate (1:1) eluates by repeated crystallisation: **11**, syrupy liquid (Found: C, 71.8; H, 8.3; N, 5.6. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{19}\text{NO}_2$ calcd. for: C, 72.8; H, 8.5; N, 5.6%); R_f 0.46 (silica gel G, 1:1 benzene-EtOAc); λ_{max} (EtOH) 284, 278 and 226 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 3.01, 3.08 and 3.72); ν_{max} (KBr) 1 635 (amide C=O) and 820 cm^{-1} (Ar); **5**, m.p. $198-200^\circ$ (Found: C, 72.6; H, 7.9; N, 5.6. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4$ calcd. for: C, 73.1; H, 8.2; N, 5.7%); R_f 0.51 (silica-gel G, 10% methanol-ethyl acetate); λ_{max} (EtOH) 278 and 229 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 3.31 and 4.27); ν_{max} (KBr) 1 620 (amide C=O), 835 and 815 cm^{-1} (Ar); m/z (relative abundance %) (M^+ , 492 (35.7)), 365 (38.6), 245 (15.2), 134 (10.5), 112 (56.8) and 77 (base peak); **8**, m.p. 98° (Found: C, 72.8; H, 7.8; N, 5.5. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4$ calcd. for: C, 73.1; H, 8.2; N, 5.6%); R_f 0.44 (silica gel G, 10% methanol-ethyl acetate); λ_{max} (EtOH) 272 and 226 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 3.355 and 4.246); ν_{max} (KBr) 1 620 (amide carbonyl), 850, 810 and 790 cm^{-1} (Ar); m/z (relative abundance %) (M^+ 492 (35.7)), 365 (38.6), 245 (15.2), 134 (10.5), 112 (56.8) and 77 (base peak).

Reaction with 1-(3',4'-dimethoxycinnamoyl)piperidine (3): 1-(3',4'-Dimethoxycinnamoyl)piperidine (2.75 g, 0.01 mol) in anhydrous 1,2-dimethoxyethane was added at 0° to a solution of sodium

naphthalenide (from 2.04 g, 0.016 mol of naphthalene) in anhydrous 1,2-dimethoxyethane under dry nitrogen. After stirring for 2 h, the reaction mixture was worked up in the usual manner and subjected to column chromatography over neutral alumina. Chromatography afforded **12** (0.58 g, 20.9%) from the petrol-benzene (1 : 1) eluates, and **6** (0.21 g, 7.6%) and **9** (1.42 g, 51.4%) from benzene-ethyl acetate (9 : 1) eluates. The latter two compounds **6** and **9** were separated from benzene-ethyl acetate (9 : 1) eluates by fractional crystallisation: **12**, m.p. 54° (Found: C, 68.9; H, 8.1; N, 4.9. $C_{16}H_{23}NO_8$ calcd. for: C, 69.3; H, 8.3; N, 5.1%); R_f 0.57 (silica gel G, 10% MeOH-EtOAc); λ_{max} (EtOH) 279 and 218 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 3.54 and 4.09); ν_{max} (KBr) 1640 (amide C=O), 855, 810 and 765 cm^{-1} (Ar); **6**, m.p. 156° (Found: C, 69.1; H, 7.8; N, 4.9. $C_{22}H_{44}N_2O_6$ calcd. for: C, 69.5; H, 8.0; N, 5.1%); R_f 0.42 (silica gel G, 10% methanol-EtOAc); λ_{max} (EtOH) 281, 232 and 217 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 3.72, 4.18 and 4.22); ν_{max} (KBr) 1630 (amide C=O), 850, 810 and 760 cm^{-1} (Ar); **9**, m.p. 140° (Found: C, 69.1; H, 7.8; N, 4.9. $C_{22}H_{44}N_2O_6$ calcd. for: C, 69.5; H, 8.0; N, 5.1%); R_f 0.37 (silica gel G, 10% methanol-EtOAc); λ_{max} (EtOH) 278 and 220 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 3.75 and 4.29); ν_{max} (KBr) 1630, 860, 815 and 760 cm^{-1} (Ar).

Dimethyl dianisyl-succinate (17)¹⁶: Diethyl succinate (5.52 g, 0.034 mol) in ether (15 ml) was added to a suspension of sodium ethoxide (2.44 g, 0.045 mol) in ether (40 ml) under anhydrous conditions. After stirring at room temperature (30°) for 20 min, anisaldehyde (4.08 g, 0.03 mol) in ether (20 ml) was added to the reaction mixture. Stirring was continued for 3 h at room temperature. It was then filtered to remove the precipitated sodium salt. Acidification of the filtrate with concentrated hydrochloric acid (6 ml) yielded a precipitate, which was filtered off, washed with ice-cold water and dried (**15**; 1.5 g, 14.1%), $C_{20}H_{18}O_6$, m.p. 258° (lit.⁶ 260–62°).

To a solution of **15** (1.18 g, 0.003 mol) in sodium hydroxide (10%) was added Ni/Al alloy (4.4 g). The mixture was heated for 1 h, cooled and filtered. The filtrate was acidified with concentrated HCl (13 ml) and the suspension extracted with $CHCl_3$ (2 × 25 ml) and resulting solid was recrystallised from acetone to yield dianisyl succinic acid (**16**; 1 g, 84.5%), m.p. 160° (lit. 160–62°).

A solution of **16** (0.83 g) in absolute methanol (15 ml) was cooled in ice, a cold ethereal solution of diazomethane was added to it and kept for 24 h. The solvent was then evaporated to obtain **17** (0.86 g, 94.8%), m.p. 90° (lit.¹⁶ 90–92°) (Found: C, 68.1; H, 6.3. $C_{22}H_{26}O_6$ calcd. for: C, 68.4; H, 6.8%); λ_{max} (EtOH) 284, 277, 227, 208 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 3.4, 3.47, 4.27, 3.86); ν_{max} (KBr) 1730 (ester C=O), 835, 815 and 740 cm^{-1} (Ar); m/z (relative abundance %)

386 (M^+), 355 (7.4), 205 (7.1), 193 (57.2), 192 (14.9), 163 (3.8), 162 (6.8) and 161 (30.4).

BH₃-THF reduction of compound 7: To a solution (0.7 ml, 1 mmol) of 1.6 M diborane in THF, **7** (0.25 g, 0.6 mmol) in THF (0.4 ml) was added over 15 min at 0°. The colourless solution was then refluxed for 1 h, cooled and 6N HCl added dropwise. THF was removed by distillation and solid NaOH added to saturate the aqueous phase. The aqueous layer was extracted with ether (2 × 10 ml). The ether extract was dried (anhydrous Na_2SO_4), and the solvent removed to get the semi-solid compound **25** (0.19 g, 81.26%), $C_{28}H_{48}N_2$ (Found: C, 82.8; H, 9.5; N, 6.6. $C_{28}H_{48}N_2$ calcd. for: C, 83.1; H, 9.96; N, 6.92%); λ_{max} (EtOH) 213 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 3.57); ν_{max} (KBr) 860 and 760 cm^{-1} (Ar); m/z (relative abundance %) 404 (M^+), 306 (12.7), 293 (19.9), 120 (4.4), 119 (3.3), 117 (2.6), 113 (1.9) and 98 (base peak).

BH₃-THF reduction of compound 5: To a solution (0.7 ml, 1 mmol) of 1.6 M diborane in THF, **5** (0.295 g, -0.6 mmol) in THF (0.5 ml) was added over 15 min at 0°. The resulting colourless solution was refluxed for 1 h, cooled and 6N HCl added dropwise. THF was then removed by distillation and solid NaOH was added to saturate the aqueous phase. The aqueous layer was extracted with ether (2 × 10 ml). The ether extract was dried (anhydrous Na_2SO_4), and the solvent was removed to get **18** (0.2 g, 71.9%), $C_{30}H_{44}N_2O_2$ (Found: C, 76.9; H, 9.1; N, 5.5. $C_{30}H_{44}N_2O_2$ calcd. for: C, 77.5; H, 9.5; N, 6.0%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1610, 1590, 800, 730 and 700 cm^{-1} (Ar).

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